

**Equipping Sports Higher Education Institutions with
Intersectional, Innovative, and Inclusive
Gender Equality Plans**

D2.2

Training materials and tools for institutional transformation

University of Gothenburg

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List of Acronyms

CoPs	Communities of practice
EC	European commission
GBV	Gender-based violence
GEP	Gender equality plan
HE	Higher education
HEI	Higher education institution
IO	Implementing organisation
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
WP	Work Package

The SUPPORTER project

SUPPORTER, “SecUring sPORTs Education thRough innovative and inclusive Gender Equality Plans”, is an EU-funded project running from April 2023 until September 2025. Launched on 19. April 2023, it aims to support eight sports higher education institutions from Central and Eastern Europe in developing their own intersectional, innovative, inclusive and impactful Gender Equality Plans which explicitly address gender-based violence and sexual harassment.

Through mutual learning and interactive exchanges, the project will seek to:

1. Identify and document systemic challenges faced by sports higher education institutions in advancing gender equality and eradicating gender-based violence.
2. Develop activities tailored to each partner institution.
3. Strengthen the sports institutions’ organisational capacity to address gender equality with an intersectional approach.
4. Foster an inclusive institutional culture by developing mutual-learning processes.
5. Strengthen networking and exchange among sports institutions and with communities of practice.
6. Foster gender-related institutional, sustainable, transformative changes in the sports institutions with a specific attention on the challenge of gender-based violence -thus ultimately fostering the institutions and their Gender Equality Plans’ inclusiveness and the overall adherence to intersectionality.

While initially partnering with eight institutions, the SUPPORTER project aspires to target and reach the wider sports ecosystem and its various organisations in Central and Eastern Europe and beyond, and in the long run contribute to wide societal changes.

Project Partners

<p>SCIENCE CONNECT YOUR PARTNER IN SCIENCE</p>	European Science Foundation (ESF), France
<p>UNIVERSITY OF GOTHENBURG</p>	Göteborgs Universitet (UGOT), Sweden
<p>SOUTH-EAST EUROPEAN RESEARCH CENTRE</p>	Kentro Erevnon Notioanatolikis Evropis Astiki mi Kerdoskopiki Etaireia, The South-East European Research Centre (SEERC), Greece
<p>УНИВЕРЗИТЕТ У БАЊОЈ ЛУЦИ UNIVERSITY OF BANJA LUKA</p>	Univerzitet u Banjoj Luci (UNIBL), Bosnia & Herzegovina
<p>University of Ljubljana Faculty of Sports</p>	Univerza v Ljubljani (UL), Slovenia
<p>UNIVERZITA KARLOVA</p>	Univerzita Karlova (CU), Czechia
<p>НАЦИОНАЛНА СПОРТНА АКАДЕМИЈА "ВАСИЛ ЛЕВСКИ" LEAGUE ASSOCIATION</p>	Natsionalna Sportna Akademiya Vassil Levski (NSA), Bulgaria
<p>LIETUVOS SPORTO UNIVERSITETAS</p>	Lietuvos Sporto Universitetas (LSU), Lithuania
<p>Universitatea de Vest din Timișoara</p>	Universitatea de Vest din Timisoara (UVT), Romania
	Georgian State Teaching University of Physical Education and Sport (GSTUPES), Georgia
	Universitatea de Stat de Educație Fizică și Sport (USEFS), Moldova

Summary

This deliverable is a mapping of existing training materials and tools within the frame of EC-funded projects implementing systemic institutional transformation towards gender equality, with a specific focus on trainings that include gender-based violence. The aim is to give an overview of existing trainings and tools in the field to provide the basis and function as an inspiration for developing the SUPPORTER training scheme.

It outlines existing trainings and tools and evaluates these according to a pre-defined set of criteria and for their applicability in the context of the SUPPORTER's Implementing Organisations (IOs).

The deliverable consists of three parts. The first part, the introduction outlines the aims, the methods and materials used for identifying and evaluating trainings and tools. The second part is the mapping, which comes in the form of an appended pdf file (also available as worksheet). The third part, the conclusions, identifies the strengths and weaknesses of existing trainings and provides general recommendations on how to build on these existing trainings.

- There are many on-line open access trainings and tools for developing GEPs; some address gender-based violence but often only in a peripheral way.
- Active participation, mutual learning, and community of practices are key methods.
- Few trainings in higher education specifically focus on sport.
- Intersectionality is often missing from the trainings.
- The target group of the trainings are most often gender agents, gender equality officers, and student networks, but leadership is missing.

1 Introduction

This deliverable is a mapping of existing training materials and tools within the frame of EC-funded projects implementing systemic institutional transformation towards gender equality, with a specific focus on trainings that include gender-based violence (GBV). It provides an overview of existing training materials and tools in the field and provides a basis for developing the SUPPORTER training scheme.

The deliverable consists of three parts. The first part, the introduction outlines the aims, the methods and materials used for identifying and evaluating trainings and tools. The second part is the mapping, in the form of an appended excel file. The third part, the conclusions, summarises the findings and describes the next steps on how the results will feed into SUPPORTER training scheme.

Aims

The aims are to map and provide an overview of existing training materials and tools within the frame of EC-funded projects in order to prepare the IOs for the systemic institutional transformation towards gender equality and the implementation of 4I-GEPs (i.e. intersectional, innovative, inclusive, and impactful GEPs), giving a specific focus to GBV.

Methods

Three approaches were used to identify relevant trainings: systematic search for EC-funded projects, identification via sister projects, and the consortium's knowledge of existing EC-funded projects. The mapping started with an identification of EC-funded projects that include trainings and tools for gender+ equality, including GBV, in higher education via a systematic search of EC-funded projects with trainings and tools aiming to implement systemic institutional transformation towards gender equality. The first search was conducted in the EC-project database CORDIS (<https://cordis.europa.eu/>). The following search terms were used: 'training', 'tools', 'gender equality plan', 'gender-based violence', 'GBV' and 'higher education'.

A total of 84 search hits were found in the first search. After removing duplicates and including only those with the aim of institutional change through gender equality plans in higher education 18 projects were selected for further consideration. All 18 projects were scrutinised for the content on a) institutional change, b) gender equality plans, and c) gender-based violence. Most of these did not address GBV, the four that did were included. A further three projects, identified from sister projects, were added as well as four projects identified by the working group. To increase the value of the mapping for the SUPPORTER project we also included selected additional trainings and tools targeting gender equality in sport organisations. In total, trainings and tools developed in 11 different projects were included in the mapping review as well as two resources on gender equality in sports and one database with useful material for developing and implementing GEPs.

Each project was reviewed in detail based on information found in CORDIS, the projects' webpages and additional online material. Trainings were identified and recorded in a matrix including name

of the project, URL-information (CORDIS and webpage), main organisation, participating countries, and the project description retrieved from Cordis. Trainings and tools were mapped in the matrix and information added, including target group, type of training, type of tools, example of methods used, type of training/tools used for addressing GBV, learning outcomes and relevance. The last part of the matrix contains an evaluation of the project including training and tools based on a pre-defined set of criteria, divided in three categories: inequality grounds covered, intersectionality and forms of violence being addressed, (Table 1).

Table 1: Mapping matrix

Theme/overview	Overall variables
Training information	Name of training, URL to resource, Access rights/licence
Content information	Content description, Themes, skills trained, Target group(s), Objectives of training, Keywords, Duration
Training and tools	Type of training used for institutional change (course, online resource, webpage etc.), e.g. mass/small group, Tools /mode used for institutional change (lecture, interactive sessions, mutual learning sessions), Examples of methods used for institutional change (e.g. Lotus blossom, word café), Type of training/tools used specifically for GBV, Learning Outcomes and relevance
Quality of trainings	General reflection, Knowledge Exchange Opportunities, Inequality grounds, Intersectionality, Forms of violence addressed
General information	Organisation/provider of training, URL Cordis, Project web page, Main organisation, Participating countries, Project description

Mapping variables

To provide a comprehensive overview of the trainings and facilitate their usefulness for the SUPPORTER project as well as other organisations searching for relevant trainings, a set of 25 variables were used (Table 2).

Table 2: Mapping variables

Name of training	The 'Name of training' column contains the name of the training as stated by the project's webpage.
URL to resource	The 'URL to resource' column contains the links to the training resource online, where available.
Access rights/licence	The 'Access rights/licence' column contains entries with access rights to the training.
Content description	The 'Content description' column contains various entries that describes the content of the trainings and contributes to the overall understanding of the training programs. The entries are diverse and may include different types of data, such as numerical, categorical, or textual.
Themes, skills trained	The 'Themes, skills trained' column contains various entries that describe the themes of the trainings and the skills it says to develop.
Target group	The 'Target group' column contains entries that list the first and second order target group of the training.
Objectives of training	The 'Objectives of training' column contains entries of the stated objectives of the training, contributing to the overall understanding of the training programs. The entries are diverse and may include different types of data, such as numerical, categorical, or textual.

Keywords	The 'Keywords' column contains the keywords of the training, as identified by the mapping.
Duration	The 'Duration' column contains entries that state the length of the training in hours and minutes.
Type of training used for institutional change	The 'Type of training used for institutional change' column contains various entries that describe the format of the training, e.g. online resource, webpage, videos etc).
Tools /mode used for institutional change	The 'Tools/mode used for institutional change' column describes the tools used such as lecture, interactive sessions, mutual learning sessions as well as more specific tools such as Miro board and Lotus blossom.
Examples of methods used for institutional change	The 'Examples of methods used for institutional change' column contains various entries that contribute to the overall understanding of the training programs. The entries are diverse and may include different types of data, such as numerical, categorical, or textual.
Type of training/tools used specifically for GBV	The 'Type of training/tools used specifically for gender-based violence' column contains various entries that list the specific tools used to address GBV.
Learning outcomes	The 'Learning outcomes' column contains various entries that describe the stated learning outcomes of the training programs. The entries are diverse and may include different types of data, such as numerical, categorical, or textual.
Knowledge exchange opportunities	The 'Knowledge exchange opportunities' column contains various entries that contribute to the overall understanding of the training programs. The entries are diverse and may include different types of data, such as numerical, categorical, or textual.
Inequality grounds covered	The 'Inequality grounds covered' column contains various entries that list the inequality grounds, e.g. gender, age, disability, ethnicity/race addressed in each of the trainings.
Intersectionality	The 'Intersectionality' column contains information on whether or not the training addresses intersectionality.
Forms of violence addressed	The 'Forms of violence addressed' column contains various entries on the forms of GBV addressed in the training.
Organisation/provider of training	The 'Organisation/provider of training' column contains the name of the organisation that developed/provided the training.
URL Cordis	The 'URL Cordis' column contains entries with the link to the project in the EC project database CORDIS.
Project web page	The 'Project web page' column contains entries with links to the EC project developing the training.
Main organisation	The 'Main organisation' column contains the name of the institution/organisation that developed the training.
Participating countries	The 'Participating countries' column contains entries listing the countries involved in the project that developed the training.
Project description	The 'Project description' column contains various entries that describes the project that developed the training (cited from Cordis).
Organisation/provider of training	The 'Organisation/provider of training' column identifies the organisations responsible for each training program.
Comments	The "Comments" column contains reflections, notes or other useful comments on the training

2. Training and tools

This section provides a summarising overview of the training and tools. For the results of the review as a detailed mapping, see Appendix 1.

In summary:

- The majority of trainings are online and available freely and with open access. They address capacity building on gender equality, and to a lesser extent GBV and intersectionality.
- Most trainings and tools available consist of online lectures, videos, and webinars. While several trainings had interactive parts, and work in sub-groups, these are not available online. Extensive trainings exist, providing open collaborative courses, open to a wider range of participants than the specific implementing organisations.
- Some trainings are in the form of workshops, coaching and/or train-the trainer sessions.
- Most trainings include resources both directed to specific groups (e.g. trainers, junior/senior researchers, administrators, HR managers) and a wider audience.
- Most of the trainings have a focus on mutual learning, e.g. through communities of practice and co-creation. These methods include opportunities for knowledge exchange. Several projects use workshops, interactive webinars and mutual learning sessions, as well as communities of practice (CoPs), to both shape and exchange knowledge. On first hand these exchanges take part between participants within the project. However, some of the projects have created a strived for knowledge exchange that goes beyond the main project participants. Such examples are GE Academy with open collaborative courses online. However, such content and scripts are not all available online. Resources such as toolkit comprise examples of concrete measures and practices.
- There are specific trainings on the six steps towards implementing a gender equality plan, with supporting materials.
- Some projects provide detailed scripts for creating a GEP, and informative descriptions of each step of the training, such as audits, planning, implementation, monitoring, self-assessment of tailored gender equality plans and organisational learning process and evaluation, and benchmarking. At hand is PowerPoints, templates, fact sheets, etc.
- Specific trainings on GBV tend to aim at improving capacities, competence, and expertise on GBV for institutions and stakeholders. These trainings include webinars, lectures, and mutual learning and knowledge-exchange seminar through round tables and discussions.
- Few trainings specifically addressing gender equality in sports have a focus on higher education.
- Few trainings and tools contain information/resources on intersectional inequalities.
- The main immediate beneficiaries of the structural change trainings on gender equality include a full range of actors. These actors could be, e.g., management, administrators, HR managers, researchers; gender experts, policymakers, NGOs, student and staff

organisations, students, gender equality innovating institutions, research funding organisations, middle and top-level management, and national sport organisations.

- The long-term beneficiaries include the whole ecosystem of research and innovation, and beyond: universities and research performing organisations, representatives of research funding organisations, policymakers at the EU and national levels, umbrella organisations, H2020 and HE sister projects, research performing organisations, civil society organisations, citizens, and the interested public.

Based on the objectives of the trainings and descriptions of the different trainings and tools, several learning outcomes are suggested:

- Increased awareness of gender equality issues and related concepts.
- Development and enhancement of various skills relevant to promoting gender equality.
- Enhanced knowledge and expertise in the field of gender equality and related policies.
- Ability to create conditions conducive to instituting institutional change in favour of gender equality.
- Improved understanding of GEP construction, monitoring, and implementation.
- Comprehensive overview of definitions and key concepts pertaining to gender equality.
- Understanding of relevant legislation concerning gender equality.
- Ability to develop effective gender equality policies and tools.
- Deeper insights into the implementation of a Gender Equality Audit.
- Establishment of valuable networks for promoting and supporting gender equality initiatives.
- Proficiency in policy mapping and analysis related to gender equality efforts.

3 Conclusions and recommendations

Most of the mapped projects that have designed relevant trainings have a focus on gender+ and include an intersectional approach. This focus is however not explicitly considered in the trainings and tools. Further, the mapping shows that GBV is not comprehensively covered in the trainings. Existing projects with trainings in GBV cover some, but not all forms of GBV, and some address prevalence, prevention, protection, prosecution, partnerships, provision of services, and/or policy (7Ps) – most often “or”, rather than “and”. Several EC-funded projects have developed specific trainings addressing GBV in workshops or webinars, but GBV is not integrated into other parts of the project. For example, gender-based violence is not an evidently included topic in trainings on GEP development or implementation. **A key recommendation from this mapping is therefore to develop comprehensive trainings that clearly and explicitly integrate GBV in the GEP creation and implementation.**

Furthermore, the mapping shows a lack of tools and trainings developed for the leadership/management level. Most trainings address the research community in general (administrative staff and students, change agents), but neglects leadership. Importantly, targeting leadership does not only mean reaching out to stakeholders in power, but as an added effect, such trainings address the importance and legitimises the issue in the wider research community/institution. **A strong recommendation is therefore to develop trainings and tools for the leadership and management levels.**

The majority of the trainings and tools are available in open access, which is of great value. Almost all trainings apply methods of active participation, mutual learning and CoPs (in different shapes) as inclusive methods for supporting and sharing learning processes and for the acquisition of knowledge. However, while the training session originally contained interactive elements, in their current available state, the tools are available as videos, recordings, and PowerPoints, which in this format necessarily are non-interactive and encompass one-way communication, even if they were interactive in their original forms.

We recommend using or gaining inspiration from existing open access trainings and tools, especially materials within projects with a capacity to grow, e.g. GE Academy has tools to train the trainer and online resources that can be used by other organisations than those included in the project. The sustainability in terms of project effects beyond the project duration, with re-useable materials, including training materials, learning resources and DOCC-platform enable continued learning. Another example is the TARGET project which can support the process of developing GEPs with clear instructions and a clear step-by-step structure to enhance a change process – easy for the participants and other organisations to follow.

The mapping review shows that the responsibility for change is often placed on gender experts, the rather unspecified “community of universities”, or scholars. **We highly recommend that the responsibility is specified and shared, not only by the leadership/management and the inner circle of experts, in order to reach out to the broader community.** In line with this, higher education institutions aiming for institutional change need to be aware of the risk of working in silos i.e.: where different disciplines and administrative units work independently instead of working together, based on institutional and cross-disciplinary exchange.

Finally, a methodological reflection: using a systematic search in CORDIS to identify relevant trainings and tools via EC-funded projects does not comprehensively cover the field: many potentially relevant projects do not show using this database as a search engine. The existing knowledge within the SUPPORTER consortium was necessary to identify the full range of potentially relevant projects from which to harvest trainings to map.

The next steps include feeding the results of the mapping into the SUPPORTER training scheme, with a selection of the existing trainings/tools to generate new, tailored trainings specifically for the SUPPORTER Implementing Organisations. These will be fully described in D3.1 “Horizontal capacity building”.

4 References

The reference list is a compilation of mapped projects, their CORDIS page, and their project page.

GE Academy:

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/824585>

<https://ge-academy.eu/welcome-to-gender-equality-academy/>

GEARING ROLES:

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/824536>

<https://gearingroles.eu/>

EIGE:

<https://eige.europa.eu/>

UniSAFE:

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101006261>

<https://unisafe-gbv.eu/>

UniswithHeart:

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/894554>

TARGET:

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/741672>

<https://www.gendertarget.eu/about/>

GENDERACTION

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/741466>

<https://h2020.genderaction.eu/>

GENDERACTIONplus

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101058093>

<https://genderaction.eu/>

ACT:

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/788204>

<https://act-on-gender.eu/>

SUPERA:

<https://www.superaproject.eu/>

<https://www.superaproject.eu/>

LetsGEP:

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/873072>

<https://letsgeps.eu/>

SPEAR:

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/824544>

<https://gender-spear.eu/>

Appendix: Mapping grid

